

KPAAM-CAM Sociolinguistic Interview Guide

Last revised February, 27 2023

Basic metadata of the recording	
Researcher	
Date	
Audio files	
Place of interview	

BIOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE	
	PERSONAL DETAILS (make sure the respondent understands you respect their right to privacy!)
1	Participant's sex
2	In which year were you born?
3	If you were to be born at home and not at the hospital, which village would have been your birth place? Give the name of the village and the quarter of birth.
4	What is your current occupation? If you do more than one job, please list all the jobs that you have done over the past 2 years.

5	Where do you currently reside? Village, quarter, compound
6	What are your names? (NB the goal is to know which networks the respondent is part of, not all the actual names he/she has → some names might be sensitive)
7	What is/are the name(s) that your father's family gave you?
8	What is/are the name(s) that your mother's family gave you?
9	What is/are your father's name(s)?
10	Do you have any other names given by any other relatives / groups? (NB the actual names are not important; our goal is to understand the networks the person is part of)
11	In which villages will local residents call you by a name that is not found in your ID? (For each of the villages in which the respondent says "yes", try to understand whether it is only one specific quarter that gave him/her the specific name. If there is one, write its name. If different quarters within the same village use different names, list the quarters. The point is not getting the actual names but what binds the respondent to a certain village)
	Abar YES/NO Notes on namegivers
	Biya YES/NO Notes on namegivers
	Buu YES/NO Notes on namegivers

	Fang	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Koshin	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Kung	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Mashi	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Missong	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Mufu	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Mundabli	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Munken	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Ngun	YES/NO	Notes on namegivers
	Other villages outside of Lower Fungom		
12	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 0 and 10 years old?		
13	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 10 and 20 years old?		
14	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 20 and 30 years old?		
15	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 30 and 40 years old?		
16	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 40 and 50 years old?		

17	In which quarters / villages did you live when you were between 50 and 60 years old?
18	In which quarters / villages did you live after you were 60 years old?
19	What are the schools that you attended?
20	The last time you were in school, what class were you attending and in which school?
	FATHER AND MOTHER
21	Where was your father born?
22	Where has your father spent his life (list all villages / quarters in which the father has spent his life with approximate periods)
23	Where did your father's mother come from (village and quarter)?
24	Please list all other families / quarters in which your father has blood relations.

25	What level of school education has your father reached?
26	What languages can your father hear or speak? Please list (also with remarks on the degree of competence)
27	Where was your mother born?
28	Where has your mother spent her life (list all villages / quarters in which the mother has spent her life with approximate periods)
29	Where did your mother's mother come from (village and quarter)?
30	Please list all other families / quarters in which your mother has blood relations.
31	What level of school education has your mother reached?
32	What languages can your mother hear or speak? Please list (also with remarks on the degree of competence)
	SPOUSE(S)

33	Where was your spouse born (village & quarter)? If you have or have had more than one spouse (polygamous man, widow, widower, divorced), please list the provenance of all your spouses, past and present, and assign a number to each one of them (e.g. spouse 1, spouse 2, etc).
34	What is the name and location of your spouse's father's family? For multiple spouses, list their father's provenances preceded by the spouse's number (see question 30)
35	What is the name and location of your spouse's mother's family? For multiple spouses, list their mother's provenances preceded by the spouse's number (see question 30)
36	What languages can your spouse hear or speak? For multiple spouses, list their languages preceded by the spouse's number (see question 30)
37	What level of school education has your spouse reached? For multiple spouses, list their level of school education preceded by the spouse's number (see question 30)
	OTHER NETWORKS
38	Where do your best friends (not relatives) come from (village & quarter)?
39	Please list the names and locations of all the savings groups (Njangi) in which you are a member.

40	Please list all the groups in which you are a member, besides families and njangis (e.g. dance groups, churches, village societies, etc). For each group, please also say where it usually meets and where the other members come from.
41	When you are sick and want to rely on traditional medicine, which traditional doctor do you go to? Where are these doctors based?
42	If you are an emigrant or an IDP, when did you leave the village (month, year)?
43	Why did you leave Lower Fungom?
44	What led you to come here instead of other places?
45	What are the differences about your occupation in LF and your current occupation? (e.g. If the respondent has always been a farmer, is he/she now a waged laborer? Was he/she farming his/her own land in LF? Whose land is he/she farming now? What kind of produce he/she works on (e.g. cash crops vs. subsistence)?

LANGUAGE SHEET - ONE SHEET = ONE LANGUAGE / LECT

Language / lect Consultant's paternal name

B1	Language name	
B2	How did you learn it and where?	
B3	When do you use it?	
B4	Are there any special occasions in which you use it? (e.g. prayers, songs, invocations, formulas) Get details.	
B5	Do you ever have dreams in this language?	
B6	What are the advantages of knowing this language?	

B7	If you did not know this language, what would be the consequences?	
B8	How do you feel when you use this language (e.g. comfortable, uncomfortable)	
B9	What do you want that people think (say) about you when you use this language?	

REMARKS (e.g. the interviewee seems shy due to the presence of the husband, the interviewee is perhaps tipsy (need to re-interview the person), etc.)